

ISic1044

I.Sicily inscription 1044

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Quarry ('Santicelli'), near A.

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, (near) Palazzolo Acreide

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140523

1. Ζώπυρος
2. ἥρωας ἀγαθός.
- 3.

Edition: PHI175446

1. Ζώπυρος
2. ἥρωας ἀγαθός
3. #⁷H
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492672

EDCS 39102198

PHI 140523

PHI 175446

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0223 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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